

Scaling Up the Efficient Manufacturing of Carbon Fiber Epoxy Composites Using Frontal Polymerization

Amirreza Tarafdar¹, Ian D. Hosein² and Yeqing Wang¹

¹Department of Mechanical & Aerospace Engineering,
Syracuse University, Syracuse, NY 13244,

²Department of Biomedical and Chemical Engineering,
Syracuse University, Syracuse, NY 13244, USA

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Background

UV-induced frontal polymerization mechanisms:

Reduce curing time from hours to few seconds or minutes

Significant reductions in cost & energy

Compatible with opaque FRP laminates

UV-induced frontal polymerization for CFRP composites

Curing time dropped from 15 hours to only 66-83 seconds!

Modeling of Frontal Polymerization in Carbon Fiber Composites

Experimental Data [1]
(Optical Measurements)

2D Model Simulations [1]

Existing models mainly focused on 1D and 2D configurations

Need to develop 3D models to study the effect of composite layups (e.g., unidirectional, cross-ply) and triggering directions for practical applications!

Part 1:

3D Modeling of Heat-Triggered Frontal Polymerization in CFRP

Problem Formulation

- Heat is generated by an enthalpic reaction during the frontal polymerization process:

$$k \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} \right) + \rho H_r \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = \rho C_P \frac{\partial T}{\partial t},$$

- The curing kinetics is described by Arrhenius equation with the classical Prout-Tompkins (PT) autocatalytic model:

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = A \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) (1 - \alpha)^n \alpha^m \frac{1}{1 + \exp [C(\alpha - \alpha_c)]}$$

Numerical Implementation

- Finite element analysis using Abaqus with: HETVAL + USDFLD user subroutines

Monomer:
Dicyclopentadiene (DCPD) resin

8-node linear heat transfer quadrilateral brick elements

Unidirectional

(b-1)

Cross-ply

(b-2)

Mesh

(b-3)

Average element size:
 $18 \times 18 \times 18 \mu\text{m}^3$

Total # of elements:
1,245,888

Model Validation

Model Validation

(a)

(b)

[2] Goli E, et al. Frontal polymerization of unidirectional carbon-fiber-reinforced composites. Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing. 2020;130:105689.

Results: Frontal Triggered from the Top Surface

Unidirectional

Cross-ply

Results: Frontal Triggered from One Side

Unidirectional

Step: Step-1
Increment: 0: Step Time = 0.000
Primary Var: SDV2
Deformed Var: not set Deformation Scale Factor: not set

Cross-ply

Step: Step-1
Increment: 0: Step Time = 0.000
Primary Var: SDV2
Deformed Var: not set Deformation Scale Factor: not set

Results: Frontal Triggered from Two Sides

Unidirectional

Y
Z X
Step: Step-1
Increment: 0; Step Time = 0.000
Primary Var: SDV2

Cross-ply

Y
Z X
Step: Step-1
Increment: 0; Step Time = 0.000
Primary Var: SDV2

Results: Frontal Triggered from Front (Perpendicular to Fiber Direction)

Unidirectional (triggered from front surface)

Unidirectional (triggered from front & back surfaces)

Results – Unidirectional Layup

- Triggering parallel to the fiber direction leads to a faster frontal propagation and higher degree of cure
- Triggering from two sides accelerates the frontal propagation

Specimen	Initial curing duration (s)	Average front velocity (mm/s)	Average degree of cure (%)
UT	0.48	1.80	94.30
UL	0.42	6.17	95.30
ULR	0.14	9.13	99.50
UF	Not fully cured	0.27	24.80
UFB	1.11	1.16	77.30

Results – Unidirectional Layup

- Thermal spike forms when the two fronts merge if triggered from both sides
- May indicate wavy patterns or non-uniform degree of cure

Results – Cross-Ply Layup

- Triggering parallel to the fiber is still preferred
- Triggering from both sides accelerates the frontal polymerization and leads to an overall higher degree of cure

Specimen	Initial curing duration (s)	Average front velocity (mm/s)	Average degree of cure (%)
CT	0.54	1.58	94.00
CL	0.56	4.59	87.80
CLR	0.17	7.27	99.40

Results – Cross-Ply Layup

- Thermal spike still exists in cross-ply laminates if triggered from two sides
- The temperature at the thermal spike is 100 degrees lower in cross-ply when compared to unidirectional laminates

Results – Unidirectional vs. Cross-Ply

- Front propagates faster in unidirectional laminates
- Front velocity changes as the front propagates, especially in UL and CL cases

Results – Unidirectional vs. Cross-Ply

- Front velocity changes as the front propagates
- Cross-ply laminate CT case exhibits a lower front velocity in different times than the UT case

Results – Effect of Fiber Thermal Conductivity

- Three different types of fibers: 10.45 W/m·K (for carbon fiber); 1.14 W/m·K (for glass fiber); 0.04 W/m·K (for Kevlar fiber).
- Front velocity drastically decreases as the thermal conductivity decreases

Results – Effect of Fiber Thermal Conductivity

- Thermal spike temperature dropped from 255 °C and 355 °C for the carbon fiber CLR and ULR cases to only 133 °C and 117 °C for the glass fiber ULR and CLR cases
- For cases with the Kevlar fiber, the thermal spike is not formed

Part 2:

Modeling of UV-induced Frontal Polymerization in CFRP (On-going work)

Problem Setup & Objective

- 2D model for unidirectional CFRP composite with epoxy frontal resin

- **Objective:** Investigate how the UV light parameters, including UV light intensity, spot size, wavelength, and distance to the specimen surface affect the frontal polymerization process

Challenges:

- Determine the accurate curing kinetics of the epoxy-based frontal resin
 - Traditional DSC does not provide the exact same UV-induced polymerization environment
 - One possible solution is to use UV-DSC to get more accurate curing kinetics

UV-induced frontal polymerizable material system	
Frontal monomer	(3,4-epoxycyclohexane)-methyl-3,4-epoxycyclohexyl carboxylate (ECC)
Photo-initiator (PI)	p-(octyloxyphenyl)phenyl iodonium hexafluorostibate (IOC-8 SbF6)
Thermal-initiator (TI)	benzopinacol

Preliminary Results

Conclusion

1. 3D models of heat triggered frontal polymerization have been used to investigate the effects of laminate layup, triggering direction, and fiber types
 - We recommend to trigger the frontal polymerization along the fiber direction as much as possible
 - We should anticipate a slower frontal propagation in cross-ply laminates
 - Triggering from multiple locations will result in thermal spikes, which could indicate occurrence of high thermal residual stresses, wavy surface patterns, and/or non-uniform degree of cure
2. A simple UV-induced frontal polymerization model for CFRP composites with epoxy-based frontal resin was modeled in a 2D configuration. Currently, we face challenges in:
 - Characterization of the curing kinetics of epoxy-based frontal resin under UV conditions
 - Can be potentially solved using the UV-DSC

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College of Engineering
& Computer Science

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Composite Materials Laboratory

Amirreza Tarafdar

Dr. Ian Hosein